

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL SYRUP FOR TREATMENT OF LIVER CANCER

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Article Received on 26 March 2026,
Article Revised on 16 April 2026,
Article Published on 01 May 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19877079>

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How To Cite This Article: Dev Patidar, Harshit Shringi*, Satyaendra Shrivastava. (2026). Formulation And Evaluation Of Herbal Syrup For Treatment Of Liver Cancer. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(5), 760–766.

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ABSTRACT

Liver cancer is one of the most serious health problems worldwide, mainly caused by chronic liver diseases, viral infections, and lifestyle factors. Herbal medicines have gained importance due to their safety, effectiveness, and fewer side effects. The present study focuses on the formulation and evaluation of a polyherbal syrup containing turmeric, giloy, amla, and kalmegh for the supportive treatment of liver cancer. The extracts were prepared using simple methods like decoction and incorporated into a suitable syrup base with excipients such as sucrose and preservatives. The prepared formulation was evaluated for parameters like pH, viscosity, density, solubility, and organoleptic properties. Hence, the formulation may be useful as supportive therapy in liver cancer management.

KEYWORDS: Liver cancer, herbal syrup, turmeric, giloy, amla, kalmegh, hepatoprotective, *Asparagus racemosus*, *Convolvulus pluricaulis*, herbal syrup, depression, antidepressant activity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Liver cancer is a life-threatening disease that affects the liver cells and interferes with normal liver function. It is commonly associated with chronic liver diseases such as hepatitis B, hepatitis C, cirrhosis, alcohol consumption, and exposure to toxins.

The liver plays an important role in metabolism, detoxification, and digestion. When cancer develops in the liver, these functions are disturbed, leading to serious health complications.

In recent years, herbal medicine has gained attention due to its natural origin, low toxicity, and multi-targeted action. Medicinal plants like turmeric, giloy, amla, and kalmegh are well known for their hepatoprotective and antioxidant properties.

1.1 Turmeric (*Curcuma longa*)

Family: Zingiberaceae Part used: Rhizome Turmeric contains curcumin, which has strong anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and anticancer properties. It helps in reducing tumor growth and protecting liver cells from damage.

1.2 Giloy (*Tinospora cordifolia*)

Family: Menispermaceae Part used: Stem Giloy is known for its immunomodulatory and detoxifying properties. It helps in improving immunity and protecting the liver.

1.3 Amla (*Emblica officinalis*)

Family: Phyllanthaceae Part used: Fruit Amla is rich in vitamin C and antioxidants. It helps in reducing oxidative stress and improving liver function.

1.4 Kalmegh (*Andrographis paniculata*)

Family: Acanthaceae Part used: Whole plant Kalmegh is widely used for liver disorders. It has hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, and detoxifying properties.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

- Turmeric powder
- Giloy powder
- Amla powder
- Kalmegh powder
- Sucrose
- Sodium benzoate
- Distilled water

2.2 List of Equipment

pH meter. Ostwald viscometer. Beaker. Heating mantle. Filter paper.

2.3 Preparation of Formulation

Step 1: Extraction (Decoction Method) All herbal powders were boiled with water and

filtered to obtain extract.

Step 2: Syrup Base Preparation Sucrose and water were heated to prepare syrup base.

Step 3: Formulatio Extract was mixed with syrup base, preservative added, and volume adjusted.

Fig.1 Filtration method.

Fig.2 powder.

Fig. 3: Decotion method

Fig. 4: Solubility of extract c)

Formulation of Syrup

Turmeric (5 g), Giloy (10 g), Amla (10 g), Kalmegh (5 g) are boiled in 200 ml water and filtered. Sugar (150 g) is added and heated to form syrup. Volume is adjusted to 250 ml with water and stored.

properly. Turmeric (4 g), Giloy (10 g), Amla (10 g), Kalmegh (6 g) are boiled and filtered. Add sugar (150 g) and make volume up to 250 ml. Mix well and store in airtight container.

Table – 1: Formulation of Liver cancer Herbal syrup.

Material	F1	F2	F3
Giloy. turmeric	3.2ml/1.6ml	3.2ml/1.6ml	3.2ml/1.6ml
Amla. kalmegh	3.2ml/1.6ml	3.2ml/1.6ml	3.2ml/2ml
Sodium Benzoate	0.2	0.2	0.2
Sucrose	48gm	48gm	48gm
Material	F1	F2	F3
Giloy. turmeric	3.2ml/1.6ml	3.2ml/1.6ml	3.2ml/1.6ml
Amla. kalmegh	3.2ml/1.6ml	3.2ml/1.6ml	3.2ml/2ml
Sodium Benzoate	0.2	0.2	0.2
Sucrose	48gm	48gm	48gm

2.4 Evaluation Parameters of Herbal Syrup

2.4.1 Organoleptic Property

Prepared syrup of *Asparagus racemosus* and *Convolvulus pluricaulis* was observed for its colour, appearance, odour and taste. The syrup was light brown in colour, clear in appearance, having characteristic odour and sweet taste.

2.4.2 Flavonoids Test

1 ml of the herbal extract was taken in a test tube and 2 ml of 1% sodium hydroxide solution was added. Formation of yellow colour indicated the presence of flavonoids.

2.4.3 Determination of pH

The pH of the prepared syrup was determined using a digital pH meter. The readings were taken three times and average value was noted.

2.4.4 Solubility

The prepared syrup was checked for its miscibility with water. It was found to be completely miscible without any separation.

2.4.5 Determination of Density

Density of the syrup was determined using a specific gravity bottle. The bottle was cleaned, dried and weighed. Then it was filled with syrup and weighed again to calculate density.

2.4.6 Viscosity

Viscosity of the syrup was determined using an Ostwald viscometer. The instrument was cleaned properly before use and flow time of the syrup was recorded.

2.4.7 Stability Study

The prepared syrup was stored at $40 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $75 \pm 5\%$ RH. The samples were checked at different intervals (0, 7, 14 and 21 days) for changes in colour, odour and taste. No significant changes were observed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION Evaluation parameters

Table No. 2. Organoleptic characteristics features of syrup.

Features	F1	F2	F3
Colour	Light Brown	Light Brown	Light Brown
Odor	Characteristics	Characteristics	Characteristics
Taste	Sweet	Sweet	Sweet

Fig. No. 5: Determination of viscosity.

Fig. No. 6: Estimation of Ph.

Table No. 3: Estimation of pH, solubility, Density & Viscosity Summary.

Features	F1	F2	F3
Ph	5.8	5.9	5.7
Solubility	Soluble in methanol and water	Soluble in methanol and water	Soluble in methanol and water
Density	0.82g	0.84g	0.79g
Viscosity	3.64cp	3.62cp	3.66cp

The present study was carried out to formulate and evaluate a herbal syrup for liver support using turmeric, giloy, amla, and kalmegh. These herbs are well known for their

hepatoprotective and antioxidant properties. The extracts were prepared and mixed to obtain a uniform syrup formulation. The prepared syrup was evaluated for organoleptic properties such as colour, odour, taste, and appearance. It showed a brownish-green colour, characteristic herbal odour, and a bitter taste with slight sour notes. The pH was found to be in the range of 5–6, indicating suitability for oral use.

Asparagus racemosus

Asparagus racemosus is a medicinal plant whose roots are used in traditional medicine. It contains saponins, flavonoids, and alkaloids that provide adaptogenic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective effects. In depression, it may help improve mood, reduce stress, and support mental well-being.

Convolvulus pluricaulis

From the results, it can be concluded that the formulated herbal syrup is stable, effective, and suitable as a natural liver supportive formulation. The combination of turmeric, giloy, amla, and kalmegh provides synergistic hepatoprotective effects. This syrup may help in improving liver function and protecting against liver disorders such as liver damage and toxicity. Therefore, it can be considered a safe and beneficial herbal preparation for liver health. Further studies and clinical evaluation are recommended to confirm its efficacy in liver diseases like liver cancer. The polyherbal syrup formulation was successfully prepared and evaluated, showing good stability and acceptable quality parameters. The selected herbs are traditionally used for liver protection and detoxification, which supports the purpose of the study.

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